

Most suitable technical methods that allow improved selective collection of OFMSW and HORECA waste.

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

In the EU over 100 million tons of biowaste are thrown away each year. Currently, 75% of this goes to landfill or is incinerated, causing major environmental problems biowaste produces greenhouse gases when it decomposes and contaminates soil and groundwater. Landfilling of biowaste goes against the principle of a circular economy and is a waste of nutrients, energy and resources for bioproducts. In this sense, SCALIBUR project aims to demonstrate innovative solutions to transform urban biowaste into high value-added products, helping cities to increase their recycling rate and creating new circular economy business opportunities.

One of the most relevant stages of the whole process of OFMSW and HORECA waste management and recovery is the stage of collection. During this first step, the biowaste from household activities and commercial establishments are gathered. During this process, an efficient system must be guaranteed, in terms of the quality and quantity of the organic waste collected (little contamination with other fractions such as plastic, glass or paper).

When establishing a type or other collection system, many relevant factors must be considered, such as the density of the population, the number of inhabitants, or even the climate, in order to develop an effective system. On the other hand, a correct analysis of the area in which the implementation will take place, can optimize the costs associated with the implementation as the maintenance of the system.

In this sense, we have carried out an analysis of the main European regions, where this system is fully established, in which the door-to-door system predominates, so that high quality levels are reached. Otherwise, increasing and optimizing also the processes of valorisation, where composting predominates and its later use as fertilizer, and anaerobic digestion, with the production of biogas, which is used as fuel or for electricity generation

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